

The three types differed little in total spikelet number, indicating that panicles with more primary branches and fewer secondary branches can be obtained without reducing total spikelets per panicle. IR varieties had more inner vascular bundles from just below the neck node and *glaberrimas* had more outer vascular bundles. Culm diameter and air space did not vary widely, but culms were thinner in IR varieties.

Correlation coefficients (Table 2) among characters show that primary

branch number was significantly correlated with number of spikelets on primary branch, total spikelets, and inner vascular bundle. In upland lines, culm thickness was correlated with all characters except number of inner vascular bundle. Culm thickness might prove to be a useful overall measure of desirable traits.

Breeding programs should transfer useful traits of *glaberrimas* and upland lines into IR varieties to increase the number of HD grains. □

Table 2. Phenotypic interrelationship between different panicle characters in 3 types of rice varieties.^a IRRI, 1988.

	1 Pbr			2 SPbr			3 Sbr		
	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
2.SPbr	.97**	.96**	.98**						
3.Sbr	.59	-.46	.77**	.49	-.34	.81**			
4.SSbr	.65*	-.46	.77**	.55	-.36	.80**	.94**	.99**	.99**
5.TSP	.93**	.56*	.86**	.90**	.68**	.89**	.79**	.45	.98**
6.IVB	.80**	.60*	.91**	.69*	.62*	.87**	.67*	.04	.54**
7.OVB	.95**	-.02	.83**	.93**	.05	.79**	.61	-.19	.73**
8.CD	.89**	.11	.89**	.85**	.24	.87**	.68*	.38	.83**
9.ASp	.85**	.15	.88**	.77**	.27	.85**	.72*	.34	.73**
10.Cth	.60	-.80**	.61*	.74*	-.05	.58*	.02	.12	.82**
	4 SSbr			5 TSP			6 IVB		
	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
2.SPbr									
3.Sbr									
4.SSbr									
5.TSP	.86**	.44	.98**						
6.IVB	.79**	.02	.54*	.83*	.61*	.66**			
7.OVB	.68*	-.21	.71**	.93**	-.12	.76**	.82**	-.29	.74**
8.CD	.71*	.37	.83**	.89**	.52*	.88**	.80**	.53*	.80**
9.ASp	.75*	.31	.74**	.86**	.51*	.81**	.81**	.62*	.83**
10.Cth	.20	.15	.82**	.56	.06	.79**	.43	-.15	.41
	7 OVB			8 CD			9 ASP		
	a	b	c	a	b	c	a	b	c
2.SPbr									
3.Sbr									
4.SSbr									
5.TSP									
6.IVB									
7.OVB									
8.CD	.94**	-.12	.75**						
9.ASp	.90**	-.07	.68**	.97**	.89**	.97**			
10.Cth	.63	-.12	.71**	.53	.30	.71**	.36	-.15	.53*

^a a = IR varieties, b = *O. glaberrima*, c = upland lines. *, ** = significant at 5% and 1% levels of probability, respectively.

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Flowering behavior of photoperiodsensitive rice germplasm of Bangladesh

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Most traditional transplanted aman rice varieties of Bangladesh are photoperiod-sensitive; however, sensitivity varies with variety and location.

Nearly 1,050 photoperiod-sensitive germplasm were grown in 1987 transplanted aman season in the BRRI experimental field (latitude 24°N) to observe flowering behavior. Materials were seeded on 20 Jul and transplanted on 22 Aug.

Varieties flowered from 15 Oct to 25 Nov (see figure). More varieties (395) flowered 1-5 Nov, synchronized with the strongly photoperiod-sensitive local variety Nizersail. Varieties flowering before 1 Nov could be moderately sensitive or have a long critical photoperiod. Those flowering later could be very strongly sensitive to photoperiod or have a short critical photoperiod. Another group of weakly photoperiod-sensitive varieties in Bangladesh flowering from late Sep to mid-Oct is not included here.

Distribution of varieties by date of flowering. BRRI, Bangladesh, 1987.

Flowering on 1-10 Nov indicates that most varieties have critical photoperiod longer (12-12.5 h) than those of Thai, Burmese, and Vietnamese varieties. For

this reason, most Bangladesh photoperiod-sensitive varieties flower too early if planted in Thailand and in similar latitudes. On the other hand, the

introduced photoperiod-sensitive varieties flower later than Bangladesh varieties because their critical photoperiod is shorter. □

Grain yield and duration of ratoon rice varieties

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To evaluate ratoon performance, we measured grain yield and duration of 10 short- and medium-duration rice varieties during 1984-85 at ACRI.

The main as well as ratoon crop received 100-22-41.5 kg NPK/ha. Immediately after rice harvest, ratoon stubbles were cleaned. Irrigation was given from day 3 onwards. All P and K plus half of N was applied 7 d after cutting. The balance of N was applied in 2 splits on day 25 (maximum tillering) and day 35 (panicle initiation).

Ratoon crop yields varied from 0.43 to 2.20 t/ha (see table). Bhavani's high

Grain yield and duration of ratoon rice. Madurai, India, 1984-85.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			Crop duration (d)	
	Main planted crop	Ratoon	Ratoon yield compared with planted crop yield (%)	Planted crop	Ratoon
Bhavani	2.5	2.2	86.6	128	78
Ponni	1.7	0.4	27.2	138	88
Puduvai Ponni	2.4	0.8	31.5	138	66
IR20	3.0	0.9	30.7	128	77
ACM8	0.8	0.7	80.0	120	67
ACM9	3.6	1.2	34.6	104	81
ACM10	2.9	1.6	54.3	104	81
CO43	2.6	0.7	25.9	135	69
CO44	2.0	0.9	46.6	120	81
MDU2	2.6	0.5	17.9	138	77
LSD (P=0.05)	0.5				

^aYellowing disease reduced yields.

yield of 2.2 t/ha was 86.6% of main crop yield. Ratoon crop durations varied from 69 to 81 d. Bhavani's field duration was 128 d in the main crop and 78 d in

ratoon crop. Analysis showed no significant correlation between ratoon crop grain yield and duration. □

Hybrid rice in rainfed environments

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Two hybrids (IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R and IR54752A/IR46R) and their parents were dry seeded (75 kg/ha) and grown under strictly rainfed conditions in lowland and upland fields of IRRI in 1987 wet season. IR46, one of the parents, was the check variety. Urea (90 kg N/ha) was topdressed on 17 Sep. Water deficit occurred 45 to 60 d after seeding (DAS) with a maximum stress of 69 kPa soil moisture tension at 20 cm soil depth and 5 kPa at 60 cm.

The table shows the performance of the F₁ hybrids and their parents under rainfed conditions. Hybrid IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R yielded

Yield and yield components of 2 F₁ hybrid rices and their parents under rainfed environments. IRRI, 1987.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	100-grain weight (g)	Filled grains (%)	Harvest index
<i>Lowland site</i>					
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R (F ₁)	3.2	1118	1.90	62.62	0.30
IR9761-19-1	0.7	788	1.28	57.05	0.18
IR46830	2.4	986	1.78	62.19	0.30
IR54752A/IR46R (F ₁)	2.2	716	2.13	56.67	0.20
IR46	2.3	926	2.03	72.09	0.28
IR54752	1.7	574	2.30	62.73	0.20
LSD (0.05)	0.4	320	0.20	22.50	0.06
<i>Upland site</i>					
IR46830A/IR9761-19-1R (F ₁)	1.0	970	1.93	64.28	0.30
IR9761-19-1	0.6	794	1.73	42.75	0.30
IR46830	0.5	910	1.65	46.60	0.23
IR54752A/IR46R (F ₁)	0.8	522	2.15	69.80	0.20
IR46	0.6	492	1.90	69.20	0.23
IR54752	0.8	490	2.20	62.50	0.25
LSD (0.05)	0.3	220	0.18	14.66	0.08

highest with 105% midparent heterosis for the lowland trial and 78% for the upland trial. Hybrid IR54752A/IR46R,

exhibited only 7% and 8% midparent heterosis in the 2 trials and yielded as much as did IR46.